

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

INVESTIGATION OF GINGER ETHANOLIC EXTRACT AS AN ANTICATARACT AGENT

Kulkarni A.S.^{1*}, Bundel S.S.², Thoke S.T.³, Attal.V.R.¹, Shital Allapure¹

¹SBNM College of Pharmacy, Hatta, Basmat, Hingoli, Maharashtra, India.

²SVP College of Pharmacy (B.Pharm), Hatta, Dist.Hingoli.

³SSS Indira College of Pharmacy, Vishnupuri Nanded.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 19/02/2018

Available online

30/09/2018

Keywords

Cataract,
Diabetes,
Oxidative Stress,
Anticataract,
Ascorbic Acid,
Ginger.

ABSTRACT

Cataract is visual impairment which arises as a result of a disturbance of lens lucidity. It is one of the leading causes of blindness worldwide which is one of the major health problems and has drawn a little attention in worldwide. The loss of vision from cataract is a major cause of blindness in developing countries. The lens is made of mostly water and protein. The proteins is arranged in a precise way that keeps the lens clear and let's light pass through it. But as we age, some of the protein and clump together and start to cloud a small area of the lens this is a cataract. Natural antioxidants are famous for their capacity to protect organisms and cells from damage due to oxidative stress, the later being considered a cause of ageing and degenerative diseases. The antioxidants present in food especially vegetables, are phenolic compounds (phenolic acids and flavonoids), Carotenoids, tocopherol Etc. The present study evaluated the in vitro Anticataract activities of Ginger Ethanolic Extract has, show magnificent a Antioxidant activity against glucose-induced cataract genesis using goat lenses. The isolated goat lenses are incubated in artificial aqueous humor and divided into four experimental groups. The Ginger Ethanolic Extract at a dose of 400µg and 500µg/ml is incubated simultaneously with glucose (55 mM) and glucose (5.5mM) for a period of 72 h. ascorbic acid (20 µg/ml) is used as the standard drug. At the end of the incubation lenses opacity is measured by photographic evaluation. The Ginger Extract shows significant inhibition of cataractogenesis of eye lenses at conc. 400µg and 500 p.p.m. The present study suggested that the ethanol extract of Ginger possesses Anticataract activity.

Corresponding author

Kulkarni A.S.

Assist. Professor,

SVP College of Pharmacy (B.Pharm), Hatta.

kamol5347@gmail.com

918605050695

Please cite this article in press as **Kulkarni A.S.** et al. Investigation of Ginger Ethanolic Extract as an Anticataract Agent. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(09).

Copy right © 2018 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Cataract is visual impairment which arises as a result of a disturbance of lens transparency. It is one of the leading causes of blindness worldwide which is one of the major health problems and has drawn a little attention in worldwide. The loss of vision from cataract is a major cause of blindness in developing countries.^[1] The lens lies behind the iris and the pupil. It works much like a camera lens. It focuses light onto the retina at the back of the eye, where an image is recorded. The lens also adjusts the eye's focus, letting us see things clearly both up close and far away. The lens is made of mostly water and protein. The protein is arranged in a precise way that keeps the lens clear and lets light pass through it. But as we age, some of the protein may clump together and start to cloud a small area of the lens. This is a cataract. Over time, the cataract may grow larger and cloud more of the lens, making it harder to see. The suspect that there are several causes of cataract, such as smoking and diabetes.^[2]

The role of behavioral habits such as smoking, alcohol intake, or drug addiction has also been investigated. During the past fifteen years, a number of cross sectional surveys have provided data on the prevalence of cataract, which indicate that cataract is by far the most common cause of blindness and visual disability worldwide. Cataract can include cases of family/genetic origin, or secondary to trauma, systemic diseases, drugs and age-related factors. Senile or age-related cataract is responsible for more than 80% of the total number of cataract cases. The proportion of cataract patients with diabetes has been found to range from 8.7 to 21%, which shows a high risk of cataract associated with diabetes. Although cataracts can be surgically removed, in many countries surgical services are inadequate or do not produce equal outcomes, and cataract remains the leading cause of blindness. Preventive interventions must be identified, perfected and delivered, through research.^[3] Ginger has long been used in traditional medicine as a cure for some diseases including inflammatory diseases. Ginger contains active phenolic compounds such as gingerol, paradol and shogol that have antioxidant, anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, anti-angiogenesis and anti-atherosclerotic properties.^[4] In this study the effect of ethanolic extract of ginger was assessed against Ascorbic acid (20 µg/ml) induced opacity in goat lenses.^[5]

MATERIAL AND METHOD :

Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) is a creeping perennial underground rhizome belonging to family Zingiberaceae^[6]

Methods Collection of plant material

The rhizome of were purchased from the local market of Hatta District of Hingoli Maharashtra. It was authenticated by Dr.I.A.Madrap Vasantrao Naik Agriculture University, Parbhani Maharashtra and a voucher specimen was kept for further reference.

Preparation of the Plant Extract

The rhizome of the plant *Zingiber officinale* were collected and washed in tap water, collected and powdered. About 20 g of the powdered rhizome material of was extracted using Soxhlet apparatus with 200 ml volumes of ethanol solvents. The solvent fractions of the extracts were evaporated by a vacuum rotary evaporator.^[7]

In-vitro Activity.

- **Requirement:**
- **Test Drug :** Orange peel Extract
- **Standard Drug :** Ascorbic Acid

Chemicals:

Potassium chloride (KCl), Sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃), Sodium chloride (NaCl), Magnesium chloride (MgCl₂), Calcium chloride (CaCl₂), NaH(PO₄)₂, Glucose, Penicillin, Streptomycin.^[8]

Procedure^[7,8]

Lens culture:

Fresh goat eyeballs were obtained from slaughterhouse was immediately transported to the laboratory at 0-4°C. The lenses were removed by extra capsular extraction and incubated in artificial aqueous humor (NaCl: 140 mM, KCl: 5 mM, MgCl₂: 2 mM, NaHCO₃: 0.5 mM, NaH(PO₄)₂: 0.5 mM, CaCl₂: 0.4 mM, and Glucose: 5.5mM) at room temperature and PH-7.8 for 72 hours. Penicillin G 32% and streptomycin 250 mg% were added to the culture media to prevent bacterial contamination. At high concentrations, glucose in the lens was metabolized through sorbitol pathway and accumulation of polyols causing over hydration and oxidative stress. This lead to cataract genesis.

Induction in *vitro* cataract:

Glucose in a concentration of 55mM was used to induce cataract at high concentrations, glucose in the lens metabolizes through sorbitol pathway and accumulation of polyols (sugar alcohols) causing over hydration and oxidative stress. This lead to cataract genesis. The lenses were incubated in artificial aqueous humor with different concentration of glucose (5.5 mM served as normal control and 55 mM served as toxic control) for 72 hours.^[9,10]

Drug study^[7]**Group I :** Aq.humor + Normal lens glucose 5.5mM (Negative control)**Group II :** Aq.humor + Glucose 55mM (Negative Control induced)**Group III :****A.** Aq.humor + Glucose 55mM+Ginger extract (400µg/ml) (Test extract Treated)**B.** Aq.humor + Glucose 55mM+ Ginger extract (20µg/ml) (Test extract Treated)**Group IV :** Aq.humor + Glucose 55mM+Ascorbic acid (20µg/ml) (std. drug Treated)**Photographic Evaluation of Lens Opacity^[9]**

Photographs of the lenses in normal and experimental groups are shown in Plate 1 which revealed that normal lens incubated with the artificial aqueous humor solution and glucose (5.5 mM) showed complete transparency. The negative control in which the lens was incubated with glucose (55 mM) a complete opacification of lens was noticed. Groups 3 in which lens were incubated simultaneously with glucose (55 mM) and the ethanolic extract of Orange peel (500 µg/ml) showed a considerable reduction in the opacity of the lens similar to that of Group 4 treated with standard drug. The result indicates a positive effect of the selected Orange peel extract on Anticataract potential by exhibiting reduction in the opacity of cataractous lenses.

The degree of opacity was graded as follows:

“0”- absence of opacity

“1”- slight degree of opacity

“2”- presence of diffuse opacity

“3”- presence of extensive thick opacity

Photographic Evaluation of Anticataract activity.**Zoom view****Fig.2: Aq.humor + Glucose 55mM (Negative Control induced).**

Normal View

Zoom view

Fig.3: Aq.humor + Glucose 55mM+Ginger extract (400µg/ml) (Test extract Treated).

Fig.4: Aq.humor + Glucose 55mM+Ginger extract (500µg/ml) (Test extract Treated).

Normal View

Zoom view

Fig.5: Aq.humor + Glucose 55mM+Ascorbic acid (20µg/ml) (std. drug Treated).

Degree of opacity shown by compound:

Normal control: Zero degree opacity is occurred, clear lens is obtained.

Negative control: Presence of extensive thick opacity, because of high conc. of glucose induce cataractogenesis.

Test (Ginger extract 400,500µg/ml): Zero degree of opacity is occurred, clear lens is obtained. Test drug inhibit cataractogenesis.

Std (Ascorbic Acid 20 µg/ml): Lens shows very slight degree of (opacity) cloudiness and initiate as clear lens.

Table no 2:- Degree of opacity shown by Orange peel extract.

Sr.No	Compound	Degree of opacity
1	Negative control	1
2	Negative control induced	3
3	Test compound (Ginger extract 400/500 µg/ml)	0
4	Std. Compound (Ascorbic Acid 20 µg/ml)	2

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:^[11]

Incubation of lenses with glucose 55 mM showed opacification starting after 8 hrs at the periphery, on the posterior surface of the lens. This progressively increased towards the centre, with complete opacification at the end of 72 hrs

DISCUSSION:^[12]

Prolonged exposure to elevated glucose causes both acute reversible changes in cellular metabolism and long-term irreversible changes in stable macromolecules. Non enzymatic glycation, oxidative stress and polyols pathway are the possible mechanisms by which high glucose concentrations induce and accelerate lens opacification leading to cataract formation. High concentrations of glucose contribute to oxidative stress by generating more reactive oxygen species at the mitochondrial level owing to increased intracellular glucose metabolism.

CONCLUSION:^[13]

The study suggested that the ethanolic extract of Ginger possessed antioxidant and Anticataract activity which might be due to the presence of Phytochemical such as flavonoids, Tannin, Free radical, polyphenols.

REFERENCES

1. Raghvendra Kurmi, Aditya Ganeshpurkar, Divya Bansal, Abhishek Agnihotri, Nazneen Dubey. Ethanol extract of *Moringa oleifera* prevents in vitro glucose induced cataract on isolated goat eye lens: *Indian J Ophthalmol* 2014;62:154-7.
2. Fact About cataract. Department of Health and Human Services, The National Institutes of Health USA.gov.Pdf; 2017:1-6.
3. Singh Amarjeet1, Sharma Pankaj, Lamba H.S., Lamba Avneet Kaur. Study of Anticataract activity of *Sesbania grandiflora* Linn & *Mentha arvensis* Linn. *Journal of Innovations in Applied Pharmaceutical Sciences*, Vol 1 (2), 2016;22-29.
4. Habib SHM, Makpol S, Hamid NAA, Das S, Ngah WZW, Yusof YAM. Ginger extract (*zingiber officinale*) has anti-cancer and anti-inflammatory effects on ethionine-induced hepatoma rats. *Clinics*. 2008;63:807-13.
5. Dharmendra Kumar, Ranjit Singh. Anticataract Activity of *Acorus Calamus* linn. Against Hydrogen Peroxide Induced Cataractogenesis in Goat Eyes. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*, Volume 11, Issue 2, November – December 2011; Article-022:112-115.
6. Vinod D.Rangari.Pharmacognosy & photochemistry, vol-I second edition, Career publication.379-380.
7. N.Rosheni .K.Nithya, S.Brindha, N.Elango, V.Goklila S.Nishmitha And Kokila .Evaluations of Anticataract Potential of *Abutilon indicum*: *Indian J.Sci.Res.* 7(1); 2016: 81-84.
8. Nimbalkar V.V., Pansare P.M., Nawale D.S., Nishane B.B. Investigation of Carvedilol as an Antidenaturing and Anticataract Agent. *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 8(5): May 2015;511-516.
9. Shabeer Ahmed N, Niyas Ahmed I, Ashar Waheed M P and Abdul Jaffar Ali H.Anticataract Activity of Ethanolic Extract of *Nigella Saltiva* on Glucose Induced Cataract in Goat Eye Lens ,*IJABPT*, Volume: 2: Issue-4: Oct - Dec -2011 .275-276.
10. Nithya K, Rosheni N, Brindha S, Nishmitha S, Elango N, Gokila V, Kokila S. Anticataract Activity of *Abutilon hirtum* on Glucose Induced Cataract in Goat Eye Lens. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res.*, 38(2), May – June 2016; Article No. 27, Pages: 145-148.
11. Cheng HM, Fagarhoilm P, Chylack LT. Response of lens to oxidative-osmotic stress. *Expt. Eye Res* 1983; 37:11-21.
12. Gupta SK, Joshi S, Velpandian T, Awor L, Prakash J, An update on pharmacological prospective for prevention and development of cataract. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*,1997;29:3-10.
13. Shashank Kumar and Abhay K. Pandey. Review Article Chemistry and Biological Activities of Flavonoids: An Overview, Hindawi Publishing Corporation The ScientificWorld Journal Volume 2013:1-16.

54878478451180222

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

